

GENDER EQUITY AND EQUALITY IN CLASSROOM

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Abstract

The issue of gender inequality is one which has been publicly reverberating through society for decades. The problem of inequality in employment being one of the most pressing issues today. In order to examine this situation, one must try to get the root of the problem and must understand the sociological factors that cause women to have a much more difficult time getting the same benefits, wages and job opportunities as their male counterparts. Savitribai Phule, the first female teacher of first women school in India is a pioneer figure. She demanded a dignity for all women, for which she along with her husband worked their entire lives. The principles of humanity, equality, liberty and justice were of utmost important to her. Gender equity is a process of being fair to women and men. Equity leads to equality. Gender equality requires equal enjoyment by women and men of socially valued goods, opportunities, resources and rewards.

Introduction:

Today we speak about Women empowerment, are we gearing our students in Equality and Equity? As long as the struggle for gender equality has existed, there have also been discussions and debates about what the concept gender equality means and how it should be used. What is the goal, how do we reach this and who are included? A concept that is relatively often used as an alternative to gender equality is gender equity. The best educational environments are those that are fair to all students, male or female in classroom.

But in many places around the world, female and male students do not always have the same chances for a good education. As students begin to notice the differences in social expectations for gender rules, the ways the teachers interact with students stand to have a great impact on their ability to participate in their education. It is important for a teacher to establish a set of rules from the beginning that promote equality.

Theoretical Background

The Gender Equality Framework draws clear distinctions and demonstrates interrelationships among the concepts of gender parity, gender equity, and gender equality. In addition to drawing out the nuances between equity and equality, the framework reinforces other key concerns such as access, quality, continuity, relevance, and learning outcomes. The framework also emphasizes the relationships between and among students and teachers and boys and girls, implying the need to transform deeply ingrained behaviours and gender norms that have negative impacts on the aspirations and life choices of girls and boys. Gender equality is a broad concept that is best understood within the wider context of social exclusion—the systematic discrimination of individuals based on characteristics such as ethnicity, race, sex, economic status, place of residence, language, or health status. Working children, indigenous children, street children, domestic workers, and children who are physically challenged, affected by HIV or AIDS, or living in conflict areas often do not have their educational needs met. In addition to addressing the injustices resulting from gender bias, a gender equality approach to achieving full participation needs to operate within the larger sphere of social justice so all children have a chance to succeed.

Objective of the study:

- To foster the acquisition and transfer of knowledge, skills and behaviour with reference to promoting gender equity and equality in classroom.

Sample for the study:

- 50 B.Ed. students-teachers.

Tool used for the study:

- Questionnaire focusing gender equity & equality in classroom.

Research Findings

The research findings are presented according to the afore mentioned research questions.

Distribution of answers is also based on respondents:

Question 1. Do you think your instruction on class behaviour is gender stereotype?

84% of responses have disagreed that they do not approach stereotypical instruction in the classroom, rather believe in presence of equal talents, capability, leadership tendency and team spirit irrespective to gender differences.

Question 2. Do you think it is important to include both the gender in classroom chores (cleaning, dusting or any other physical activity)?

The majority of respondents accept the fact that equal distribution of classroom chores make the young talents free from of all gender bias practised in the society.

Question 3. Is creating mixed gender groups for classroom projects and discussions, a must call for promotion of gender equality and equity?

92% responses agree that creating mixed groups for classroom projects brings equality and equity, right from the classroom itself before exposure to outer stereotypical world.

Question 4. What can you do to help fight gender inequality in classroom?

58% believe that equal distribution of all activities in and out the class makes the students have a broad mindset of equality and equity.

Question 5. As a teacher, what the sources of information have helped you to understand gender equality and equity?

Communication transfers knowledge best and thus through information transit in terms of technology plays a great role in promoting gender equality and equity, where we get all information women achievers overcoming all barriers.

Question 6. Do you think encouraging gender equity and equality in classroom leads the way for bright nation? The responses of this question depicts that the education and the young educators have a clear image of treating all genders fairly leading to a radiant democracy.

Question 7. To what extent does the curriculum content of secondary school in India covers gender equity? The curriculum of secondary school does not give uniform preferences to both genders, as it is been averagely agreed by the respondents.

Question 8. What are the changes do you want to be implemented through text book for bringing up gender equality and equity?

These are some of the responses best suited to this survey :

- Life achievement of women in different fields, supportive and encouraging men and activities that should be done by both the gender.
- Implementing lessons that teaches both genders are equal and letting them know each others have nothing in differences.
- Updated data, giving LGBTQ examples for more awareness.
- By removing stereotypical images from textbook where in only women are shown cooking, stringing flowers and so on.
- Stress more on women's contribution in Indias's freedom struggle as well as growth and development of India.
- For bringing up gender equality, throughout text I want to implement various changes like there should be equality in content given by male scientists as well as female scientists.

CONCLUSION:

Gender inequality is still being a huge issue which is prevalent in most of the streams where males are considered superior to females. Women need to fight to vote, for equal pay and to have male dominant jobs, but still have lower incomes and are more likely to live in poverty than men.

More than 90% of the student teachers in this survey considered that classroom setup should be reformed and modified for a better, exquisite and sumptuous environment where all genders lead a life. This can be done through inclusive participation of both the genders, equal division of tasks, supportive straight talks from the teachers, parents, role models, selection of correct school material, activities that add values and more of involvement of families which makes the future generation combat gender bias.

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